

Membrane potential based assay for SLC34A1 using HEK293 JumpIn SLC34A1 OE cells

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Assay description

FLIPR® membrane potential dye measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, upon activation of SLC34A1. The assay allows the detection of ion channel and transporter modulation by increasing or decreasing the fluorescent signal as cellular membrane potential changes. When cells are depolarized dye enters the cells, causing an increase in fluorescent signal, conversely, cells hyperpolarization results in dye exit and decreased fluorescence (Figure 1). SLC34A1 is the type IIa sodium-dependent phosphate cotransporter that plays a critical role in reabsorption of inorganic phosphate (Pi) by renal proximal tubular cells. SLC34A1 mediated transport is electrogenic and preferentially transports divalent Pi (HPO_4^{2-}). It functions with a $\text{Na}^+:\text{Pi}$ stoichiometry of 3:1 which results in a net inward movement of one positive charge per transport cycle.

Figure 1. Principal of a FLIPR® membrane potential dye assay. The assay measures changes of charges across the cell membrane, consequence of channels and transporters modulation. The fluorescent signal increases in intensity during membrane depolarization as dye follows the positively charged ions inside the cell. During membrane hyperpolarization, fluorescent signal decreases in intensity as dye follows the positively charged ions out of the cell.

Assay protocol

HEK-293 JumpIN-SLC34A1 cells were subjected to pharmacological characterization.

Cell preparation

Cells were detached from 80-90% confluent flasks and seeded at 10'000 cells/well in black-clear bottom poly-D-Lysine coated 384 well plate in medium without the selective antibiotics and incubated 24 hours at 37°C, 5% CO₂. At the same time of seeding cells were induced with 0.5 µg/mL Doxycycline (not induced control and mock cell line in parallel).

Membrane Potential assay

Before dye loading, cells were washed with 25µL/w of Tyrode's buffer Na^+ free (30 min at room temperature). Then buffer was manually removed, and cells were loaded with FMP-Blue-Dye (1X dye dissolved in Tyrode's buffer Na^+ free as indicated in the manufacturer manual) for 30 min at RT (with or without LC-1 30 µM). Plates were analysed at FLIPR^{TETRA} reader using a lexco 510 - 545nm / λ_{em} 565 - 625 nm filter.

To test pharmacology 20 µL/well of substrates: Na_2HPO_4 or KH_2PO_4 (2X prepared in Tyrode's Buffer with different Na^+ concentrations (0, 130, 200 mM thus 0, 65, 100 mM final concentration), starting from 1 mM final concentration, 1:3 dilution steps (8 concentrations, only buffer included) were online injected at the plate reader and fluorescent signal recorded.

Data analysis

FLIPR^{TETRA} measurements obtained from different well replicates were analysed by using the Screenworks software (Molecular Devices, Version 3.0.1.4). Absolute Response (RFU) is obtained applying "Subtract Bias on Sample: n" (where n = Timepoint of compound injection) whereas Assay Window Response ($\Delta F/F_0$) is obtained applying "Response over Baseline" correction (where Baseline = Timepoint -1 and -2 before activator injection) and "Background Subtraction". Data were then exported as Area Under the Curve (AUC). Mean and standard deviation of each replicate were calculated on the exported data with Excel software, then values were used to create

sigmoidal dose-response curves (variable slope) and to calculate EC50/IC50 values with GraphPad PRISM software (Version 6).

Target data

SLC	SLC34A1
Synonyms	Sodium-Dependent Phosphate Transport Protein 2A, NPT2a
SLC sub-family	Solute Carrier Family 34 (Type II Sodium/Phosphate Cotransporter)
UniProt ID	Q06495
RESOLUTE Cell ID	CE06CC-B (HEK-SLC34A1-WTOE-p5-6)

Assay data

	Compound name (1)	Na ₂ HPO ₄
	PubChem CID	24203
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # 71643
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 32 µM
	Compound name (2)	KH ₂ PO ₄
	PubChem CID	516951
	Vendor (catalogue #)	Sigma Aldrich, # P9791
	Mode of action	Substrate
	Standard value type (i.e EC50, PoC, etc)	EC ₅₀ = 39 µM

Discussion

The Membrane Potential Assay for SLC34A1 showed a specific and dose-dependent cell depolarization upon substrates injection. The best results were obtained injecting the substrates in buffer containing 130 mM Na⁺, while in the absence of Na⁺, the transporter was not functional, as expected. LC-1 inhibitor was also tested (30 μM, 30 minutes incubation) and completely abolish the signal.

Cross references

- RESOLUTE report at [Zenodo](#).